

Methods of binding of application elements to the main expression

Zokir Zikriyovich Saidov

Samarkand State Foreign Language Teacher

Abstract: This article talks about the methods of connecting an additional element to a basic expression. In this case, attention is paid to both the theoretical and practical significance of the study of applied constructions.

Key words: adverbial element, adverbial construction, sentence, conjunction

The issue of application construction is primarily a stylistic issue. That is why linguists often study this side of it, leaving aside its structural and semantic features. However, it would be possible to get complete information about this issue when it is studied in all respects. The main essence of the article is related to the reflection of the structural and semantic nature of adjunctive constructions that have a continuous character in the modern German language. Here, we pay more attention to the structural and semantic status of continuous constructions. In terms of the way in which the additional elements are connected to the main expression, the additional constructions are divided into two types:

1. Applied elements connected by means of fasteners;
2. Without connecting means - additional elements connected by intonation.

In the first type, connecting tools serve to implement syntactic relations between the components of the application constructions. It is in the function of conjunctions that there are some words that act as conjunctions and conjunctions.

In the second type, the syntactic relations between the main expression and the additional elements are realized without connecting means, that is, by intonation. In adverbial constructions, adverbial elements are in the form of a compound sentence without connectives. However, in terms of content, such additional elements together with the main expression are aimed at expressing a mutually

integrated general idea, and the additional element is pronounced with flat intonation in pronunciation. Similar properties have the additional constructions of continuous nature that we will analyze here.

In the study of the structural and semantic features of the adjunctive constructions with a continuous character, we will follow the examples collected on the basis of the artistic works of contemporary German writers. Our observations confirm the extremely large number of adjunctive constructions with continuous character in modern German literary language and their structural diversity. Let's consider the structural and semantic features of continuous constructions. As it is known, the application forms several structural types with the meaning features expressed in the construction, composition. We will consider these structural types separately.

a) Place - additional elements with location and direction meanings:

1. Der Hauptsender vom zehnten Stock hatte gesagt, wenn jetzt er Hausherr sei, dann könnte endlich einmal den Ort richten, lasten Lechner hatte erweilert, der Hauptsender sollte ihre nicht schwach anreden, und der Hauptsender, (der ausgeschämte Hund) hatte den Eichner finally hinausgeschmissen.

In seinem eigenen Haus (L. Feuchtwanger Erfolg, S. 416).

2. Auf der Bettseite unter Glas hing ein Bild Stalins, das Thomas nicht kannte. In dem verschlag unter der Treppe, in dem er lange nicht Robert Lohse gehaust hatte, waren mehrere Photographien und Zeitungsbilder mit Reißnageln an den unregelmäßigen Wänden befestung gewesen. Aus Spanien, aus Frankreich (A. Seghers. Das Vertrauen. P. 57). The examples given above confirm our opinion that adjunctive elements are often formed to define, complete and explain some part of the main expression. In fact, the additional elements "In seinen eigenen Haus" and "Aus Spanien, aus Frankreich" were created to clarify, complete, and give additional meaning to the underlined parts of the main expression. This confirms the idea that additional elements can appear only when the main expression is structurally and semantically independent. Because if we remove these two

auxiliary elements, our main expression remains in the form of a simple complex subordinate clause. However, some underlined clauses in this compound sentence structure are not ambiguous. For example, in our second sentence, the photos are hanging on the wall, but it remains unclear where these photos came from.

if we insert the auxiliary element "Aus Spanien, aus Frankreich" into this sentence:

First, the structure of a complex sentence with a subordinate clause is broken and becomes an auxiliary construction; Secondly, additional meaning is added to the undefined content, it is filled, defined. In such adjunctive constructions, adjunctive elements are formed at the request of some clause, but the syntactic relations between the main expression and the adjunctive element can be restored by the first means of the main clauses. But in the study of syntactic communication, some elements that cause these additional elements may also be involved. For example, in our first example, the phrase "Hatte hinausgeschmissen" ie "sent out" or "destroyed" requires a direct identification of the place where the event took place.

To clarify this point, an additional item "in seinem eigenen Haus" appears.

Such events can also be seen in the following examples:

3. Infanteristen trabten mit klappernden Maschinengewehren nach vorn kurze Zeit später preschte der schwere Geländewagen des Generals vorbei.

Nach Westen.

(B. Brecht Dreigroschenroman).

4. Er richtet den Lichtstrahl seitwärts Räts ins Gebüsch.

Woher kommt das? „Aus Angerhausen“

(F. Walter. Ein Katzensprung S. 152).

Payt ma'nosiga ega bo'lgan ilovali elementlar:

5. Wolverhampton blieb stehen . Also gut, wir werden darüber reden. Aber jetzt nicht, und hier nicht, Meine Gattin und mein Sonn bedürfen der Rune. Kommen sie morgen früh bei mir.

Zwischen neun und zehn.

(K. Karl Heinz. Das Gespenst von Black Rose Gaste, s. 105).

References

1. Адмони В. Г. Пути развития грамматического строя в немецком языке. М., 1973. -С. 171.

2. Крушельницкая К.Г. К вопросу о смысловом членении предложения. Вопросы языкознания, №5. 1956.

3. Распопов И.П. Актуальное членение предложения. Уфа, 1961.-112 с.

4. Реферовская Е.А. Лингвистические исследования структуры текста. Л., 1983. -215 с.

5. Шафиро М.Е. К вопросу о присоединении. Вопросы синтаксиса и стилистики рус. литературного языка. Куйбышев, 1963. с. 59-77.